

MAIN FACTORS AFFECTING CLASS MANAGEMENT ABILITY IN ISLAMIC PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

Teachers who work in the world of education, especially in the classroom, need good skills in managing the class so that the class becomes conducive to enabling students to learn well. Teachers who have expertise in classroom management need an appropriate educational background and instructor experience. This study was conducted to analyze the relationship between teacher education background and teaching experience with classroom management skills. This research belongs to the type of quantitative research which consists of two independent variables, namely teacher education background (X1) and teaching experience (X2), and dependent variable, namely classroom management (Y). This research is a population research conducted in all Islamic primary school in East Pekalongan sub-district. In analyzing the data researchers used simple and multiple linear regression analysis techniques with the help of SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solution) as a statistical tool. The results showed that the educational background of teachers affected the ability of teachers in class management at Islamic primary school East Pekalongan with a t count of 2,942 and a significance value of $0.004 \leq 0.05$, and a coefficient of determination of

0.109. Teaching experience has an effect on the ability of class management at ISLAMIC PRIMARY SCHOOL East Pekalongan with a t count of 5.088 and a significance value of $0.000 \leq 0.05$, and a coefficient of determination of 0.267. Teachers' educational background and teaching experience together have an effect on the ability of class management at Islamic primary school East Pekalongan with an F count of 17.559 and a significance value of $0.000 \leq 0.05$, and a coefficient of determination of 0.334.

Keywords: Teacher education, teaching experience, classroom management.

1. Introduction

The teacher is the component that most influences the creation of quality educational processes and outcomes (Zabolotniaia et al., 2020). In other words, improving the quality of education must start with the teacher and end with the teacher as well. Teachers as educators who deal directly with students are required to have expertise in the academic field or have a special educational background in certain branches of knowledge (Zuhaeriah et al., 2020). The breadth and depth of the teacher's knowledge and teaching experience is also one of the determinants of student learning outcomes. In the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers Article 8 states that "a professional teacher is a teacher who has four competencies (abilities), namely pedagogical, personal, social, and professional competencies". Another thing that needs to be put forward in relation to professionalism, namely that there is no single teaching method that can be used in every teaching situation, therefore classroom management skills are needed for teachers. Therefore, in learning every teacher is also required to always learn in order to be able to improve the quality of learning (Pham et al., 2019).

Relevant academic backgrounds provide knowledge and skills for each teaching material and use various learning methods in the learning process,

providing many alternatives for teachers to take initiative and be creative to achieve learning output according to the indicators already in the syllabus and lesson plans (Mallidou et al., 2018). Fulfillment of academic qualification standards regulated in Regulation of the Minister of National Education (PERMENDIKNAS) number 16 of 2007 article 1 paragraph (1) states “every teacher is required to meet the academic qualification standards and teacher competencies that apply nationally”, these rules must be implemented and fulfilled by all teachers at all levels of education including teachers. Islamic primary school. Islamic primary school teachers must have a minimum academic qualification of Diploma 4 (D4) or undergraduate (S1) in the field of Islamic primary school education obtained from an accredited study program (Junusi et al., 2019).

Islamic primary school teachers are different from middle or secondary school teachers. Elementary school teachers with a classroom teacher system are required to be more capable of managing the class, as well as being able to master 5 main subjects including Indonesian, Mathematics, Science, Social Sciences, PPKn. Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (Islamic primary school) is the most basic level of formal education in Indonesia (Adinugraha & Muhtarom, 2021), equivalent to elementary school, the Madrasah Ibtidaiyah curriculum is the same as the primary school curriculum (Suraya et al., 2020), it's just that in the Islamic primary school there is a larger portion of Islamic religious education. In addition to teaching subjects such as elementary school, there are also additional religious lessons such as: Alquran, Hadith, Aqidah Akhlaq, Fiqh, Islamic Cultural History, and Arabic (Sholehuddin et al., 2021; Adinugraha, Ema Hidayanti, Agus Riyadi, 2018).

Becoming a good classroom teacher is a task that can be carried out effectively and efficiently by someone who is prepared to master the ability to manage the class through special education or training, so that the utilization of classroom teachers must meet the requirements and qualifications or competencies according to the type and level of the school where they work

(Festo, 2021). Therefore, classroom teachers need appropriate qualifications who already have an in-depth knowledge of primary school education and Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (McDermid, 2020). However, the facts found in the field are that there are still many Islamic primary schools that do not have an Islamic primary school background.

Another thing that also determines the ability of teachers to manage the class is their teaching experience (Kurniawan et al., 2020). The teaching experience of teachers is one of the factors in supporting the implementation of teaching and learning activities. Teaching experience is an important concern in determining the success of learning. The teaching tenure of the teacher is expected to have a lot of teaching experience. The teaching experience of teachers is one of the factors in supporting the implementation of teaching and learning activities. The working period of teaching experience is counted since the person concerned is a teacher, both as a civil servant and a non-civil servant. For Non-Government Employees teachers, there must be physical evidence that they teach at the school. In pursuing their field of work, the teacher's experience always increases. As the working period increases, it is hoped that the teacher will have more experience (Hidayati et al., 2020). So that the ability of the teacher in managing the class will also be better because the level of difficulty that the teacher finds in learning is getting less and less in certain aspects along with the increasing experience as a teacher.

Teachers who have adequate teaching experience will positively determine the success of the learning process, on the other hand, teachers who have inadequate teaching experience will hinder the learning process (Ak & Gökdaş, 2021). Teachers who are rich in teaching experience should be more responsive in dealing with problems related to the teaching and learning process, because the experience they have can be used as a reference while carrying out their duties as a teacher (Berger et al., 2018). These experiences are closely related to increasing work professionalism, in this study what is meant by the

professionalism of a teacher in managing the classroom (Fernández-Berrocal et al., 2017). Teachers who have served in the world of education for a long time must be better at managing the classroom than teachers who have served for several years, but in fact there are classroom teachers who have long teaching periods but are less able to condition the classroom environment (Copriady et al., 2018).

East Pekalongan District has 8 Madrasah Ibtidaiyah. Of all the teachers of the Islamic primary school class in East Pekalongan, there are still some class teachers who are not in accordance with their educational background, namely non-Islamic primary school, there are even classroom teachers with non-educational educational backgrounds. Class teachers who are not in accordance with the educational background will reduce their level of ability in class management. Madrasah Ibtidaiyah in East Pekalongan currently implements the 2013 (thematic) curriculum which has been on average since 2017. Based on an interview the researcher conducted with Mr. Abdul Ghofur as head of the Islamic primary school NU Baros East Pekalongan, he appreciates the new curriculum changes. From the Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbud) because every reform that is implemented is of course aimed at making it better and in its implementation there must be several obstacles because each policy will have its advantages and disadvantages. Thematic learning is an integrated learning strategy that uses themes to link several subjects to one another so that they can provide meaningful experiences to students. Thematic learning places more emphasis on active student involvement.

East Pekalongan is a sub-district that will be examined by researchers regarding the ability of classroom management by classroom teachers in thematic learning which is influenced by the educational background and teaching experience of the teacher (Berbegal-Mirabent et al., 2018). Being a teacher who has good class management skills is not easy, and there are still teachers who complain about creating a conducive classroom situation. The cause of classroom

conditions is difficult to be conditioned due to the absence of students' readiness to accept lessons, teachers lack readiness in teaching, and chaos often occurs in class (Koyama & Niwase, 2019).

As for the obstacles faced when managing the class, namely when students without fear of leaving and entering the classroom at will and the commotion in class which causes the material to be conveyed less well. While the problems that occur in managing the class, namely the teacher's assignments, which include a lot of academic assignments and supporting tasks, various things can happen at the same time in class while some work must be done at almost the same time, the teaching process in class can be said to be sufficient (Kellen & Antonenko, 2018). Fast, unpredictable classroom climate, historical conditions in the previous class affecting at the next level (List et al., 2019).

Given the problems in class management that occur, a teacher must be able to overcome and be able to control the classroom conditions to return to its original condition, therefore teachers who have good classroom management skills are needed (El-Kassem, 2019). Based on temporary observations obtained by researchers that in the Islamic primary school in East Pekalongan there are classroom teachers with different academic backgrounds and varied teaching experiences, the researchers suspect that this affects the ability of class teachers to manage the class. Therefore, researchers will conduct research on the effect of teacher educational background and teaching experience on classroom management ability in Islamic primary school of East Pekalongan.

The research objective was to determine the effect of the classroom teacher's educational background and classroom teaching experience on the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. As well as to determine the effect of the educational background of teachers and teaching experience together on the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan.

2. Methods

Research uses a type of quantitative research that focuses on correlation research, aiming to find out whether there is a relationship. Data collection techniques are observation, questionnaires, and documentation. In this study, there are two independent variables, namely X1 (Teacher Educational Background) and X2 (Teaching Experience), and 1 dependent variable, namely Y (Classroom Management).

3. Educational Background of Islamic Primary School Teachers

From the results of the questionnaire on the educational background of teachers, it is known that the highest score is 4, obtained by 29 respondents. While the lowest score was 2, obtained by 7 respondents. Then to determine the distribution of scores in the intervals, you must first determine the number of interval classes. In determining the interval class, there must be at least two interval classes and a maximum of one-third of the scores in the range. The number of interval classes in this study were grouped into 3 interval classes with very high, high, moderate, low, and very low categories.

The average value of the questionnaire results for the educational background of the teacher (X1) was 3.30 and was in the interval 2.7 - 3.3. So it can be seen that the educational background of the teacher is in the sufficient category. In the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan, there are various educational backgrounds of classroom teachers. From the results of the research that has been carried out, there are 29 class teachers with an educational background of S1 Madrasah Ibtidaiyah or Elementary School Teacher Education, 37 class teachers with a non-education background of Madrasah Ibtidaiyah or Elementary School Teacher Education, and class teachers with an S1 background. Non-education totaling 7. The total of all teachers is 73.

4. Teaching Experience of Islamic Primary School Teachers

From the results of the teaching experience questionnaire, it is known that the highest score is 10 obtained by respondents number 8, 19, 37, 50, and 57. While the lowest score is 2 obtained by respondents number 39, 40, 41, 47, 48, 52, 63, 66, 69, and 70. Then to determine the distribution of scores in the intervals, one must first determine the number of interval classes. In determining the interval class, there must be at least two interval classes and a maximum of one-third of the total scores in the range.¹¹⁸ The number of interval classes in variable X₂ is grouped into 3 interval classes with high, moderate, and low categories. The average value of the results of teaching experience (X₂) is 5.60 and is in the interval from 4.6 to 7.1. So it can be seen that the teaching experience is in the sufficient category.

Class teachers at the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan have varied teaching experiences. There are teachers who have taught for a long time, up to 20 years and there are also teachers who teach in a matter of months. Teaching experience is related to the tenure of the teacher as well as the training that the teacher has attended. Every teacher has different teaching experiences because each teacher also has different teaching periods

From the results of the research that has been carried out, 17 class teachers with teaching experience > 21 years, 10 class teachers with 16-20 years of teaching experience, class teachers with 11-15 years of teaching experience live 15, classroom teachers with 6 teaching experience - 10 years totaling 11 and class teachers with teaching experience < 1 - 5 years totaling 20.

5. Class Management of Islamic Primary School Teachers

Y variable data obtained through a questionnaire, namely class management. Based on the results of data processing, it can be seen that in the classroom management instrument that was tested using a used questionnaire of 30 items, there were 25 valid item numbers and 5 invalid item numbers.

From the results of the class management questionnaire, it is known that the highest score was 139 obtained by respondent number 37. Meanwhile, the

lowest score was 96 obtained by respondent number 16. Then to determine the distribution of scores in intervals, first must determine the number of interval classes. In determining the interval class, there must be at least two interval classes and a maximum of one-third of the scores in the range. The number of interval classes in variable Y is grouped into 5 interval classes with very high, high, moderate, low, and very low categories.

Thus, the average value of the class management questionnaire (Y) is 121.89 and is in the interval 114 - 122. So it can be seen that class management is included in the sufficient category.

6. Results and Discussion

Simple Linear Regression of Educational Background on Classroom Management Ability

To determine the effect of teacher education background on classroom management abilities, it was analyzed using simple linear regression (X1) to Y. The output results of simple linear regression are as follows:

Table 1. Simple Linear Regression Model Teacher Education Background on Classroom Management

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.330 ^a	.109	.096	9.462

The table above shows the magnitude of the relationship between the teacher education background variable (X1) and the classroom management ability variable (Y). Based on the information from the table, it is known that the R value is $0.330 > 0.5$, which means that the educational background of the teacher has a relationship.

The value of determination (R square) was 0.109. This shows that the magnitude of the influence of teacher education background on classroom management is 10.9% and the remaining 89.1% is influenced by other variables.

Table 2. Anova of Teacher Education Background on Classroom Management

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	775.214	1	775.214	8.658	.004^b
Residual	6357.115	71	89.537		
Total	7132.329	72			

a. Dependent Variable: Classroom Management

b. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher Education Background

Furthermore, to test the regression model, it can be done by looking at the calculated F value and the significance value in the table above. Based on the information from the table, it can be seen that the F count obtained is $8,658 > 2.74$ (F table can be seen in the attachment), and the significance value is $0.004 < 0.05$. The conclusion that can be drawn is that H_0 is rejected, which means that the educational background of the teacher has a significant effect on the ability of classroom management.

Table 3. Teacher Education Background Coefficient on Classroom Management

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	92.135	5.870		15.697	.000
Background Teacher Education	5.138	1.746	.330	2.942	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Classroom Management

In the table above, namely Coefficients, shows the regression equation to estimate the class management ability (Y) which is influenced by the educational

background of the teacher (X1). From the output, the Y coefficient value is 92,135 and the X1 coefficient is 5,138. So the regression equation is $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

$$Y = 92,135 + 5,138 X$$

The explanation of the regression equation above is that without a teacher educational background, the class management ability is 92,135, while every time there is an increase in the educational background of the teacher, the class management ability will increase by 5,138. The regression equation is used as a basis for estimating the ability of classroom management which is influenced by the educational background of teachers.

Simple Linear Regression Teaching experience on Classroom Management Ability

To determine the effect of teaching experience on classroom management abilities, it was analyzed using simple linear regression (X2 against Y). Simple linear regression is used to see a one-way relationship with a more specific variable, where the X2 variable (teaching experience) functions as the independent variable that affects it, and the Y variable (class management ability) is the dependent variable that is affected. The results of the simple linear regression output are as follows:

Table 4. Teaching Experience and Classroom Management Experience
Regression Model

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.517 ^a	.267	.257	8.580

a. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching Experience

b. Dependent Variable: Classroom Management

The table above shows the magnitude of the relationship between the teaching experience variable (X2) and the classroom management ability variable (Y). Based on the information from the table, it is known that the R value is

0.517 > 0.5, which means that the educational background of the teacher has a relationship. The value of determination (R square) is 0.267. This shows that the magnitude of the influence of teacher education background on classroom management is 26.7% and the remaining 73.3% is influenced by other variables.

Table 5. Anova of Teaching Experience on Classroom Management

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1905.533	1	1905.533	73.617	.000 ^b
Residual	5226.796	71	37.185		
Total	7132.329	72			
a. Dependent Variable: Class management					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Teaching experience					

Furthermore, to test the regression model, it can be done by looking at the calculated F value and the significance value in the table above. Based on the information from the table, it can be seen that the F count obtained is 73,617 > 2.74 (F table can be seen in the attachment), and the significance value is 0.000 < 0.05. The conclusion that can be drawn is that Ho is rejected, which means that teaching experience has a significant effect on classroom management skills.

Table 6. Teaching Experience Coefficient on Classroom Management

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	97.097	2.563		37.880	.000
Teaching experience	2.142	.421	.517	5.088	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Class management					

In the table above, namely Coefficients, this shows the regression equation to estimate the class management ability (Y) which is affected by the teaching experience (X2). From the output results, the Y coefficient value is 97.097 and the X2 coefficient value is 2.142. So the regression equation is: $Y = \alpha + \beta X$

$$Y = 97,097 + 2,142 X$$

The explanation of the regression equation above is that without teaching experience, the class management ability is 97,097, whereas every time there is an increase in teaching experience, the class management ability will increase by 2,142. The regression equation is used as a basis for estimating the ability of classroom management which is influenced by teaching experience (Oliver et al., 2011).

Multiple Regression Results of Educational Background and Teaching Experience on the Ability of Teachers In Classroom Management

To determine the educational background of teachers (X1) and teaching experience (X2) on the ability of teachers in classroom management (Y), were analyzed using multiple linear regression. Multiple linear regression is used to see the effect of more than one independent variable on a dependent variable. The results of the multiple linear regression output are as follows:

Table 7. Regression of Teacher Educational Background, Teaching Experience and Classroom Management

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.578 ^a	.334	.315	8.237
a. Predictors:(Constant), Teaching experience, teacher education background				
b. Dependent Variable: Class management				

In the table above, namely the summary model, it can be seen that R is multiple correlation, namely the correlation between two or more independent variables on the dependent variable. In multiple linear regression analysis, the

number R shows the simultaneous correlation (together) between the teacher education background variable (X1) and teaching experience (X2) on the classroom management variable (Y). As for the direction and provisions of the correlation, that is, if the sign of correlation is (+) then the direction of the correlation is positive, conversely if the sign of correlation (-) then the direction of the correlation is negative. If the correlation value is ≥ 0.5 , the correlation is strong. Conversely, if the correlation value is ≤ 0.5 , the correlation is weak. From the output results, the R value is $0,578 \geq 0.5$, so the correlation is strong and positive.

Meanwhile, R Square shows the coefficient of determination, which means the percentage of the effective contribution of teacher education background (X1) and teaching experience (X2) to classroom management skills (Y). The value of R Square was 0.334, meaning that simultaneously the percentage of the effective contribution of teacher education background and teaching experience to classroom management skills was 33.4%, while the remaining 66.6% was influenced by many other factors called “unexplained factors”, outside the background behind teacher education and teaching experience on classroom management skills. Adjusted R Square, this is the adjusted R Square and is usually used when there are more than two independent variables. The standard error of the estimate is 8,237, this is a measure of prediction error. This means that the error in predicting the class management ability is 8,237.

Table 8. Anova Teacher Education Background, Teaching Experience of Classroom Management

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	2382.768	2	1191.384	17.559	.000 ^b
Residual	4749.561	70	67.851		
Total	7132.329	72			
a. Dependent Variable: Class management					

b.Predictors: (Constant), Teaching experience, teacher education background

In the table above, namely Anova, the ANOVA technique or analysis of variance is used to test the significance of whether X1 and X2 affect Y by using the F test and its significance value. Based on the table, it can be seen that F calculated is $17.557 > 2.74$ and the significance value is $0.000 < 0.05$, which means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So the conclusion is that the teacher's educational background and teaching experience together (simultaneously) have a significant effect on the ability of classroom management.

Table 9. Teacher Education Background Coefficients, Teaching Experience and Classroom Management

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	84.517	5.344		15.815	.000
Teacher education background	4.073	1.536	.261	2.652	.010
Teaching experience	1.987	.408	.448 0	4.867	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Class management					

In the table above, namely Coefficients, shows a multiple regression equation to estimate the class management ability (Y) which is influenced by the educational background of the teacher (X1) and teaching experience (X2). From the output results, the Y coefficient value is 84.517 while the X1 coefficient value is 4.073 and the X2 coefficient value is 1.987. So the regression equation is: $Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2$

$$Y = 84,517 + 4,073 X_1 + 1,987 X_2$$

Based on the regression equation above, without a teacher educational background and teaching experience, the class management ability is 60,692,

whereas every time there is an increase in the educational background of the teacher, the class management ability will increase by 4.073 and every time there is an increase in teaching experience, the class management ability will increase by 1.987. The multiple regression equation is used as the basis for estimating the ability of classroom management which is influenced by educational background and teaching experience.

Based on the hypothesis test above, it can be concluded that together the factors of teacher education background and teaching experience determine the ability of teachers in classroom management. Class management as referred to in this research is classroom management carried out by classroom teachers in thematic learning. The results of the data analysis show that the hypothesis is in accordance with that proposed in this study. The assumption that there is a significant effect of teacher education background and teaching experience on classroom management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan is proven. The higher the educational background of the teacher and the teaching experience of the parents, the higher the classroom management skills of the class teacher. Conversely, the lower the teacher's educational background and teaching experience, the lower the ability of classroom management (Chuang et al., 2020).

On the other hand, the teacher education background factor independently determines the ability of teachers in class management at the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. The higher the educational background of the teacher, the higher the ability of classroom management (Shahzan et al., 2018). Likewise, on the other hand, the lower the educational background of the teacher, the lower the ability of class management to be. Even so, however, not all teachers with low educational backgrounds have low classroom management skills either. This is because there are still many other factors that influence the ability of class management outside the educational background of teachers.

Research Description of Educational Background and Teaching Experience on the Ability of Teachers in Classroom Management

Based on the results of the research data, the educational background of the class teachers in the Islamic primary school, East Pekalongan sub-district was in the sufficient category. In the linear regression analysis, the value of R square was obtained 0.109, which means that the contribution of the teacher's educational background to classroom management is 10.9%, while the remaining 89.1% is influenced by other variables. This shows that the educational background of teachers has a sufficiently positive contribution even though it is not dominant in class management.

Furthermore, the teaching experience of teachers in Madrasah Ibtidaiyah at East Pekalongan sub-district was also in the sufficient category. In linear regression analysis, the value of R square was obtained 0.267, meaning that the contribution of teaching experience to the ability of class management was 26.7%, while the remaining 73.3% was influenced by many other factors. This shows that the teaching experience of teachers has a positive contribution even though it is not dominant in class management.

Then based on the results of linear regression analysis, it provides information that the educational background variables and teaching experience variables together have an effect on classroom management (Iswan et al., 2020). This is evidenced by the calculated F value of the equation for 17.559 with a significance of 0.000 ($0.000 < 0.05$). This is in accordance with the explanation that educational background and teaching experience are two aspects that affect the professionalism of a teacher in the field of education and teaching (Wahono & Chang, 2019). In this study, what is meant by professional teachers is the ability to manage the class.

Professional teachers will be able to manage the class well (Bakar, 2018). Because with good classroom management, a conducive learning situation will be created (Julia et al., 2020). If the educational qualifications are appropriate and have good teaching experience, then they will be able to manage the class well so

that the learning process will be carried out as expected and the learning outcomes will be maximized (Setiawan & Sugiyanto, 2020).

Therefore, in order for a teacher to have high or good class management skills, the teacher must have sufficient or long teaching experience (Sewell, 2020). Because, it turns out that the educational background of teachers is only slightly able to influence the ability of teachers to manage the class (Torkar & Šorgo, 2020). However, this can be different if the research is carried out with different variables (To Khuyen et al., 2020). Because there are still many other factors outside the educational background of teachers and teaching experience that affect the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan.

7. Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis through proving the hypothesis of the problems raised regarding the effect of teacher education background and teaching experience on classroom management at Islamic Primary School Pekalongan, the following conclusions can be drawn: Teacher education background partially has a significant effect on teacher ability in management class at the Islamic primary school in East Pekalongan. This is indicated by the tcount value of 2.942 with a significance value of $0.004 \leq 0.05$, with a determination coefficient of 0.109, which means that 10.9% of teacher education background variables affect the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. While the rest is influenced by many other factors called unexplained factors outside the educational background of teachers on the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. The higher the educational background of the teacher, the higher the ability of classroom management. Teaching experience partially has a significant effect on the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. This is indicated by the t-count value of 5.088 with a significance value of $0.000 \leq 0.05$, with a determination coefficient of 0.267,

which means that 26.7% of the teaching experience variable affects the ability of teachers in class management at the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. While the rest is influenced by many other factors called unexplained factors outside teaching experience on classroom management abilities. The higher the teaching experience, the higher the classroom management ability. The teacher's educational background and teaching experience simultaneously have a significant effect on the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. This is indicated by the Fcount value of 17.559 with a significance value of $0.000 \leq 0.05$, with a determination coefficient of 0.334, which means that 33.4% of teacher education background variables and teaching experience affect the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. While the rest is influenced by many other factors called unexplained factors outside the teacher's educational background and teaching experience on the ability of class management in the Islamic Primary School of East Pekalongan. The higher the teacher's educational background and teaching experience, the higher the ability of classroom management.

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